

Different type of searching mechanism

INTRODUCTION:

The procedure of conducting a web search is straightforward and involves merely submitting a query to the search engine. In response, the search tool will search its web-based information databases for the information it needs and pull the results that are pertinent to the query. Searching is an iterative process; unless the precise information is found, one must continue to refine their query.

Search engines, subject directories, and metasearch tools are the three main categories of search tools that most people use to locate what they're looking for on the Internet. Compared to subject directories, search engines are larger and more general. Multiple search engines provide the results for Meta Search Tools.

SOME SEARCHING TOOLS:

The searching tools (which) follow a pattern-matching algorithm. There are numerous types of searches that can be conducted using these search tools; however, the effectiveness of each method may vary. Although some tools excel in specific contexts, others may prove less efficient. This variability is crucial to understand because it can impact the results obtained.

- **Keyword Search :**

Keyword searching is the process of conducting a search using a keyword. Anywhere in the content or in the metadata area, a keyword may appear. The recall value of this type of search is higher. Users input specific keywords (or phrases) and the search engine retrieves documents that contain those terms. However, the process is not always straightforward. Because of this, users may find themselves sifting through numerous results. Although the technology is advanced, it can still yield irrelevant content at times. But, with patience and precision, users can navigate the complexities of search engines effectively.

Example :

Keywords in academic research are similar. For example, let's say your research question is "how does cyberbullying affect teenagers' mental health?"

You should first consider what the key ideas are. That would be teens, mental health, and cyberbullying in this instance.

Next, think about the terms or phrases that will best assist you locate information related to each of the primary concepts. Attempt to come up with appropriate synonyms as well, keeping in mind that there are typically other ways to say the same idea.

For instance, you would likely want to list students and adolescents for teenagers, but you might also think about using high school as a synonym for students.

- **Boolean Search :**

Boolean operators are logical AND, OR, and NOT. Boolean search is the term used when Boolean operators are utilized in the search process. When merging multiple words under specific conditions, the operators are utilized. Combinatorial search is another name for this type of search.

AND

All documents containing all of the keywords that appear at both ends of the AND operator will be retrieved by this operator.

Example :

Library AND Information

output :

Only documents that contain the phrases Library and Documentation will be returned by the aforementioned query.

OR

All documents that contain all of the keywords that appear at both ends of the OR operator will be retrieved by his operator.

Example:

Library OR Information

output:

The above query will retrieve all documents which contains both the terms Library and Documentation.

NOT or AND NOT

These operators improve the search result's accuracy. These operators can be used to make the query more precise. When a search word is preceded by the capitalized AND NOT operator, documents containing that term are removed.

Example:

The query may be "Driver" AND NOT "Screw" if the user is seeking information about drivers and does not want documents that contain information on screw drivers.

- **Phrase Searching:**

One of the most accurate ways to search is to use a specific phrase or word combination. To achieve this, enclose a phrase or terms in quote marks. For instance, search "bending toward justice" if you want to find a phrase like that, or "political activism" if you want to ensure that the database looks for political activism as a unified term rather than individual words. Sometimes using quotation marks can restrict a search too much, while other times it's not clear if they're necessary. Because of this, it may be wise to try both using and not using them in searches.

Example:

Since Thomas Hardy is a well-known author and the subject heading is already established, there is no need to enclose his name in quotation marks in the MLA International Bibliography search shown below. However, in order for the search results to include that exact phrase, the words Victorian science must be enclosed in quote marks.

Searching: **MLA International Bibliography** | [Choose Databases](#)

Thomas Hardy	Select a Field (optional) ▾	Search
AND ▾ "victorian science"	Select a Field (optional) ▾	Create Alert
OR ▾ darwinism	Select a Field (optional) ▾	Clear ?

+ -

[Basic Search](#) [Advanced Search](#) [Search History](#) ▶

Fig : Phrase Searching (source : <https://libguides.bc.edu/advancedsearch/phrase>)
(The image is taken for education purpose)

- **Proximity Search :**

The phrase "search" is one of the most often used proximity operators in proximity searching. When search terms are encapsulated in quote marks, it means that the search results must have them in precisely the same sequence and close together. For instance, a search for "climate change" would only yield results that contained that exact phrase, not the terms "climate" and "change" in any combination.

Boolean operators are another type of proximity operator. By combining search phrases, users can generate more sophisticated inquiries using terms like "AND," "OR," and "NOT." In contrast to a search for "climate change OR global warming," which would yield results containing either of those terms, a search for "climate change AND global warming" would only yield results containing both of those search terms.

- Adjacency operators, usually denoted by a tilde (~) sign, can be used in conjunction with a number value that indicates the maximum distance permitted between terms to conduct a proximity search. For instance, you could use the following search string to locate pages that have the phrases "apple" and "pie" within three words of one another: pie and apple.
- You can utilize wildcard searches, which let you look for several forms of a term using a wildcard character, in addition to adjacency operators. The asterisk (*), which can stand for any number of characters, is the most widely used wildcard character. For instance, you could use the search phrase comp* to find papers that contain any term that begins with the letters "comp."
- You can use curly brackets {} or square brackets [] to search for more than one query term in a single field. For instance, you could use the following search phrase to locate publications that have the words "cat" or "dog" in the title field: title: (dog OR cat)
- Alternatively, one might employ curly brackets to conduct a proximity search on several terms within a singular field. For instance, if you wish to locate documents that include the terms "apple," "pie," and "recipe" within five words of one another in the title field, you could utilize the subsequent search string: title:{apple pie recipe}~5. However, this method can be particularly effective because it narrows down the results significantly. Although sometimes challenging, mastering these techniques is essential for efficient information retrieval.

There are two type of Proximity:

- Near Proximity
- Exact Proximity

- **Free Text Search :**

This subject explains how Search responds to the search terms you enter in a free-text query. When you type text into the Console search box, it is automatically processed as a free text search. Any category that Search provides can be searched using a free text search. This covers resource searches, Console pages from various services, and documentation.

If you choose to view the resource results after submitting a free text search, you can use the resource explorer to work with the results. There are two search modes available in the resource explorer: basic and advanced.

Search looks for matches between search phrases and indexed field values. This means that for resources, Search assesses the value of all indexed resource properties, ranging from resource type-specific attributes to common attributes (apart from the resource type property). This covers all page display names and service groupings for services. This comprises the topic's title and contents for documentation purposes.

Examples:

For example, a free text search for the term "net" queries all resource types, service pages, and documentation for the string "net" in any indexed field. If the string appears as part or the whole of a value anywhere in an indexed field, Search considers the found item a matching result. Search doesn't require exact matching, but an exact match does improve a result's ranking.

The text on either side of the delimiter is treated by Search as an independent search term if the free text search contains a delimiting character (such as a hyphen). A free text search for "2020-04" for instance looks for the strings "2020" and "04". A potential result is a match if it contains either string.

- **Truncation Search :**

Truncation refers to the concatenation of words; in other words, when the root string of certain terms is searched, it yields all the derivatives derived from that specific root string. There are three types of truncation (based on various techniques). However, it's important to note that each method serves a unique purpose, because the efficiency of the search can significantly differ. Although truncation may seem straightforward, its implications can be quite complex. This understanding is crucial for effective information retrieval.

- **Left Truncation**
- **Right Truncation**

Features :

- **To apply truncation, type the word's root followed by the truncation sign.**
- **Any ending of that root word will be included in the results that the database returns.**
- **Database-specific truncation symbols can differ, but typical ones include *,!,?, or #.**

examples:

child* = child, childs, children, childrens, childhood

genetic* = genetic, genetics, genetically

- **Strig Search:**

The combination of text, numbers, and occasionally special characters that a user types into a search form on an application to locate particular kinds of information is known as a search string. A search engine receives the search phrase from the application, evaluates it, and then looks up the desired information. The information may originate from a database, file server, vast dispersed collection of unstructured data, or another kind of data storage. The user is then presented with the search results after they have been returned to the calling program.

The sort of search being done, the capabilities of the application and search engine, and the type of target data all influence the precise structure of a search string. Sometimes a user fills out a search form with text boxes, drop-down menus, or other choices for

specifying more intricate search parameters, while other times they input the search term straight into a straightforward text box.

- **Faceted Search:**

Users are permitted to refine search outcomes according to numerous attributes (or categories), including: price, brand and ratings. However, this functionality can enhance the overall experience. Although it might seem straightforward, the ability to filter results is crucial because it allows for a more tailored exploration of options.

Example:

Amazon and other e-commerce websites employ faceted search to assist customers in selecting products.

- **Semantic Search :**

Transcends mere keyword matching to grasp the meaning and context of the search query

(1) It takes into account synonyms, related concepts and user intent; however, this approach is more nuanced. Although keywords are important, understanding the underlying meaning is crucial

(2) Because of this, the process becomes highly sophisticated and effective in delivering relevant results.

REFERENCE:

- ❖ *Free Text Search*. (n.d.). (C) Copyright 2024. <https://docs.oracle.com/en-us/iaas/Content/Search/Concepts/freetextsearch.htm>
- ❖ Tripathi, Aditya. (2011). *Search Tools*. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/349732381_Search_Tools
- ❖ *LibGuides: Database Search Tips: Truncation*. (n.d.). <https://libguides.mit.edu/c.php?g=175963&p=1158679>
- ❖ *Proximity Searching: What You Need to Know - Luigi's Box*. (n.d.). Luigi's Box. <https://www.luigisbox.com/search-glossary/proximity-searching/>
- ❖ *RUSH Library: Guide to the Basics: AND, OR, NOT - Which to Choose? Boolean searches explained*. (n.d.). <https://library.rush.edu/basics/booleanBasics>

